

Decay Heat and Inventory Predictions for Fusion and Fission Events, FISPACT-II & JEFF-4.0, JENDL-5, ENDF/B-VIII.1 libraries

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ABSTRACT

Modelling nuclide inventories and radiation source terms as a function of time is fundamental to the operation, safety and environmental assessment of a nuclear power plant. Regulatory authorities require proof that simulations are correct or predictably conservative. The time evolution of decay heat and nuclide inventory are two important metrics when modelling the irradiation of a fusion power plant and the burn-up characteristic of fission fuel. The uncertainty and validity of these time-evolving metrics are fundamental to the operation and safety case of a plant and the safe handling of irradiated fuels and structural components. Verification and Validation of these simulations by direct comparison to key integral experimental results for both fission and fusion are strategic processes. This drives the analysis of the input nuclear data, associated uncertainties, simulation protocols indicating any inaccuracies and deficiencies which can lead to erroneous results.

Keywords: Decay heat, Inventory, Modelling, Fuel characterization, Nuclear Data

1. INTRODUCTION

In power plants decay power arises after shutdown from the energy released in the decay of the products of neutron interaction by α , γ and β emissions. Computation of the decay power is performed by sophisticated computer codes, which solve the large number of coupled differential equations governing the generation and decay chains for the many nuclides involved. They rely on a large volume of nuclear data that includes both neutron activation-transmutation-depletion cross sections and radioactive decay data.

While most traditional time-dependent inventory and observables codes rely upon one bespoke nuclear data library, the ability to harness any dataset affords a unique opportunity to cross-check data and provide feedback which ultimately improves the code/data system. By performing a verification and validation on FISPACT-II with all the most recent, major international nuclear data libraries, this exercise goes beyond demonstrating the capabilities of the code/data system in simulating decay heat and inventories, giving precise information on which nuclides should have their fission yield, production yield or decay data re-evaluated and in which library.

To ensure that this validation is as robust as possible, a thorough effort has been made to revisit as many high-quality decay heat experiments with complementary neutron spectra, irradiation schedules, measurement techniques and nations of origin. Simulations from theoretical fission bursts to full-day irradiations have been performed, using a variety of nuclear data combinations, and compared with the available experiments.

Little experimental data on decay power existed for most fission reactor materials other than reactor fuel, or for materials under high energy irradiation conditions typical of fusion, until a series of experiments were performed using the Fusion Neutron Source FNS facility at the Japan Atomic Energy Agency JAEA. Many elements and some alloy micro-samples were irradiated in a simulated D-T neutron field for times up to 7 hours and the resulting decay power generated was measured for cooling times of up to a year or more. Using the highly sensitive Whole Energy Absorption Spectrometer

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(WEAS) method, both β and γ emission decay energies were measured at selected cooling times as early as a few tens of seconds after the irradiation ended.

2. CODE AND LIBRARIES

FISPACT-II [1] has been used to perform this validation exercise. The FISPACT-II code allows the use of a variety of neutron, gamma, charge particles induced cross section data, decay data (DD) and neutron-induced fission yield (nFY) libraries, of which the following are used:

- JEFF-3.3/4.0 [2] International neutron induced libraries containing nFY, sFY and decay files
- JENDL-4/5. [3] Japanese neutron induced libraries containing nFY, sFY and decay files
- ENDF/B-VIII.0/1 [4] American neutron induced libraries containing nFY, sFY and decay files

The various libraries contain not only different data for the same nuclides but also cover different sets of nuclides. This is summarised in Table I, where the columns show the number of nuclides with neutron-incident, decay (DD), neutron-induced fission (nFY) and spontaneous fission yield (sFY) files, respectively.

Table I. Overview of the number of target nuclides which have files within each nuclear data library

Library	n-incident	DD	nFY	sFY
JEFF-3.3/4.0	562/593	3851/3852	19	3
JENDL-4/5	406/795	1380/4071	31/36	9/10
ENDF/B-VIII.0/1	556/557	3821	31	9

Comparisons are initially made between paired neutron-induced reaction, fission yield and decay data from the same continent

3. DECAY HEAT GENERATED BY FISSION EVENTS

The thermal fission of ^{235}U results in the release of some 200 MeV which is carried by the numerous outgoing particles. In a typical fission, more than 80% of these 200 MeV manifests as kinetic energy of the two main fission fragments, while approximately 10 MeV is carried by neutrinos and some 4-8 MeV are taken by each of the following: prompt neutrons, prompt gammas, fission product betas and fission product gammas. The β - and γ -decays of the fission products are commonly referred to as the decay heat due to the fission. These are of tremendous importance to the nuclear power industry as they are generated over time-scales relevant to reactor operation and the wider fuel cycle. The events at the Fukushima Daiichi power plant underline this point; even though decay heat represents a small fraction of total reactor power, the integrated energy output after shutdown is more than enough to break safety limits in a reactor or storage pool.

3.1. Fission Decay Heat Experiments

Fission yields are generally a function of energy, and several experiments have been performed with various nuclides and neutron energies to determine heat output as a function of time. In this article the data are drawn from the sources listed in Table I, with numerical data accessible in CoNDERC [5]. Neutron spectra are separated into either thermal (th) or fast (f), denoted with a subscript on the fissile nuclide. These datasets represent the most complete, comprehensive ensemble to date. This study, and its predecessor, aim to simulate ideal, theoretical irradiations that focus solely on one target making use of specific FISPACT-II keywords such as FISYIELD and FISCHOOSE, OVER and ACROSS, or ALAM, all triggering dedicated protocols.

3.1.1. Pu-239 Simulations

The results are organized by target nuclide, showing the experiments depicted previously compared to previous and newer versions of the nuclear data libraries depicted by solid and dashed lines respectively. Only a subset of the available Pu239 simulations is showed in Figs. 1-3.

Table II. Decay heat data sources with a primary author, experimental information and indicative year.

Author, Institute	Nuclide(s)	Method	Irrad. (s)	Year
Fisher, LANL	$^{232}\text{Th}_f$, $^{233}\text{U}_f$, $^{235}\text{U}_f$, $^{238}\text{U}_f$, $^{239}\text{Pu}_f$	γ	< 1	1964
McNair, UKAWRE	$^{235}\text{U}_{th}$, $^{239}\text{Pu}_{th}$	β	10-1E5	1969
MacMahon, SRRC	$^{235}\text{U}_{th}$	β	10-1E4	1970
Scobie, SRRC	$^{235}\text{U}_{th}$	β	1E4-1E5	1971
Lott, CEA	$^{235}\text{U}_{th}$	Total	1E2-5E3	1973
Yarnell, LANL	$^{233}\text{U}_{th}$, $^{235}\text{U}_{th}$, $^{239}\text{Pu}_{th}$	Total	2E4	1978
Jurney, LANL	$^{233}\text{U}_{th}$, $^{235}\text{U}_{th}$, $^{239}\text{Pu}_{th}$	γ	2E4	1979
Murphy, UKAEA	$^{235}\text{U}_f$, $^{239}\text{Pu}_f$	β	1E5	1979
Dickens, ORNL	$^{235}\text{U}_{th}$, $^{239}\text{Pu}_{th}$, $^{241}\text{Pu}_{th}$	γ & β	1-100	1980
Baumung, Karlsruhe	$^{235}\text{U}_{th}$	Total	200	1981
Akiyama, JAEA	$^{233}\text{U}_f$, $^{235}\text{U}_f$, $^{238}\text{U}_f$, $^{239}\text{Pu}_f$	γ & β	10-300	1982
Akiyama, JAEA	$^{232}\text{Th}_f$, $^{nat}\text{U}_f$	γ	10-300	1983
Johansson, Uppsala	$^{235}\text{U}_{th}$	γ & β	4-120	1987
Tobias Berkeley NL	$^{235}\text{U}_{th}$, $^{239}\text{Pu}_{th}$	Stat.	-	1989
Schier, UM Lowell	$^{235}\text{U}_{th}$, $^{238}\text{Pu}_f$, $^{239}\text{Pu}_{th}$	γ & β	<1	1997
Ohkawachi, JAEA	$^{235}\text{U}_f$, $^{237}\text{Np}_f$	γ & β	10-300	2002

More context and details on the specific experimental conditions listed are provided in [6]

Figure 1. The beta and total heat (left), gamma and total heat (right) from a thermal pulse on Pu-239.

Figure 2. The beta and tota heat (left), gamma and total heat (right) from a fast pulse on Pu-239.

Figure 3. The total decay heat from a thermal irradiation of 20,000 s on Pu-239 (left), the gamma decay heat from a fast 0.02 s irradiation of Pu239 (right).

3.1.2. Meta-analysis

To achieve a full understanding of how each library and sub-library performed, residuals, C/E and χ^2_ν values were calculated Table III and Fig. 4. Such meta-analysis help interpreting the evolution and cross section, fission yield or decay data differential impact on the decay heat metric.

Table III. Weighted average C/E for each neutron and heat type for the JEFF sub-library updates, given as percentages, across all Pu-239 simulations

Neutron Type	Heat Type	3.0 [%]	4.0 (XS Only) [%]	4.0 (nFY Only) [%]	4.0 (DD Only) [%]	4.0 [%]
Fast	Total	99.3 ± 0.5	99.7 ± 0.5	99.4 ± 0.5	99.4 ± 0.5	98.9 ± 0.6
	Gamma	89.7 ± 0.6	90.8 ± 0.5	89.7 ± 0.6	90.4 ± 0.6	86.1 ± 0.7
	Beta	100.8 ± 0.3	101.9 ± 0.3	100.8 ± 0.3	100.8 ± 0.3	101.9 ± 0.3
Thermal	Total	96.8 ± 0.2	96.8 ± 0.2	99.5 ± 0.3	96.8 ± 0.2	96.6 ± 0.3
	Gamma	97.9 ± 0.3	97.3 ± 0.6	97.6 ± 0.4	98.2 ± 0.3	98.0 ± 0.4
	Beta	96.1 ± 0.2	96.1 ± 0.2	95.8 ± 0.2	96.1 ± 0.2	95.8 ± 0.3

Figure 4. The change in residuals as a percentage for each JEFF sub-library update, averaged across all simulations, grouped by neutron and heat type, for Pu-239

Table IV. FNS decay heat Experimental and Calculated results Iridium (left) and Nickel (right)

Times	FNS Exp.	TENDL-2025	JEFF-4	ENDF/B-VIII.1	JENDL-5	Times	FNS Exp.	TENDL-2025	JEFF-4	ENDF/B-VIII.1	JENDL-5		
Min.	$\mu\text{W/g}$	$\mu\text{W/g}$	E/C	E/C	E/C	Min.	$\mu\text{W/g}$	$\mu\text{W/g}$	E/C	E/C	E/C		
1.10	2.44E-02 +/- 30%	3.63E-02 +/- 4%	0.67	0.67	0.19	0.76	0.58	4.11E-02 +/- 6%	6.00E-02 +/- 22%	0.69	0.70	0.76	0.92
1.35	3.01E-02 +/- 19%	3.29E-02 +/- 4%	0.92	0.92	0.25	1.00	0.83	4.38E-02 +/- 6%	5.52E-02 +/- 21%	0.79	0.81	0.91	1.05
1.60	2.87E-02 +/- 18%	2.99E-02 +/- 4%	0.96	0.96	0.25	1.01	1.08	4.18E-02 +/- 6%	5.09E-02 +/- 21%	0.82	0.84	0.96	1.08
2.03	2.50E-02 +/- 17%	2.55E-02 +/- 4%	0.98	0.98	0.24	0.97	1.33	3.71E-02 +/- 6%	4.71E-02 +/- 20%	0.79	0.81	0.96	1.03
2.63	1.69E-02 +/- 15%	2.08E-02 +/- 4%	0.81	0.81	0.18	0.74	1.58	3.35E-02 +/- 6%	4.37E-02 +/- 20%	0.77	0.79	0.96	0.99
3.25	1.43E-02 +/- 14%	1.72E-02 +/- 4%	0.83	0.83	0.17	0.69	2.02	2.95E-02 +/- 6%	3.85E-02 +/- 19%	0.77	0.79	1.02	0.97
4.12	1.11E-02 +/- 12%	1.38E-02 +/- 4%	0.81	0.81	0.15	0.60	2.62	2.56E-02 +/- 6%	3.28E-02 +/- 18%	0.78	0.81	1.14	0.96
5.22	8.98E-03 +/- 10%	1.12E-02 +/- 4%	0.80	0.80	0.15	0.53	3.22	2.20E-02 +/- 7%	2.84E-02 +/- 17%	0.77	0.80	1.25	0.93
6.32	8.02E-03 +/- 8%	9.74E-03 +/- 5%	0.82	0.82	0.15	0.49	4.07	1.84E-02 +/- 7%	2.37E-02 +/- 16%	0.78	0.81	1.45	0.91
7.93	7.13E-03 +/- 7%	8.84E-03 +/- 5%	0.81	0.81	0.15	0.45	5.17	1.53E-02 +/- 7%	1.96E-02 +/- 16%	0.78	0.82	1.80	0.88
10.05	6.61E-03 +/- 5%	8.61E-03 +/- 6%	0.77	0.77	0.16	0.42	6.27	1.37E-02 +/- 7%	1.69E-02 +/- 16%	0.81	0.87	2.28	0.90
12.15	6.92E-03 +/- 5%	8.79E-03 +/- 7%	0.79	0.79	0.18	0.44	7.88	1.19E-02 +/- 7%	1.42E-02 +/- 17%	0.84	0.90	3.00	0.90
15.27	7.38E-03 +/- 5%	9.20E-03 +/- 7%	0.80	0.80	0.20	0.46	9.95	1.04E-02 +/- 8%	1.22E-02 +/- 17%	0.85	0.93	3.69	0.90
19.37	7.91E-03 +/- 5%	9.68E-03 +/- 7%	0.82	0.82	0.22	0.48	12.05	9.32E-03 +/- 8%	1.08E-02 +/- 18%	0.87	0.95	4.00	0.91
23.48	8.22E-03 +/- 5%	1.00E-02 +/- 7%	0.82	0.82	0.22	0.49	15.15	8.02E-03 +/- 7%	9.25E-03 +/- 18%	0.87	0.95	3.89	0.91
27.60	8.48E-03 +/- 5%	1.03E-02 +/- 7%	0.83	0.83	0.22	0.51	19.25	6.58E-03 +/- 7%	7.75E-03 +/- 18%	0.85	0.93	3.39	0.88
34.72	8.66E-03 +/- 5%	1.05E-02 +/- 7%	0.83	0.83	0.23	0.52	23.32	5.54E-03 +/- 7%	6.59E-03 +/- 18%	0.84	0.92	2.93	0.87
44.83	8.70E-03 +/- 5%	1.05E-02 +/- 7%	0.83	0.83	0.23	0.53	27.42	5.00E-03 +/- 7%	5.67E-03 +/- 18%	0.88	0.96	2.69	0.91
54.93	8.70E-03 +/- 5%	1.03E-02 +/- 7%	0.85	0.84	0.23	0.54	34.48	3.92E-03 +/- 8%	4.51E-03 +/- 19%	0.87	0.94	2.15	0.88
	mean % diff. from E		21	21	419	77	44.58	3.00E-03 +/- 8%	3.45E-03 +/- 20%	0.87	0.92	1.68	0.87
	mean χ^2		10.59	10.62	3453.51	219.55	54.68	2.58E-03 +/- 8%	2.83E-03 +/- 23%	0.91	0.95	1.47	0.89
								mean % diff. from E		23	16	40	9
								mean χ^2		13.68	9.02	41.94	2.00

4. DECAY HEAT GENERATED BY FUSION EVENTS

The Fusion Neutron Source FNS facility at the Japan Atomic Energy Agency JAEA was used to irradiate samples materials. Many elements and some alloy micro-samples were irradiated in a simulated D-T neutron field for times of 5 minutes and 7 hours and the resulting decay power generated was measured for cooling times of up to a year or more. Using the highly sensitive Whole Energy Absorption Spectrometer (WEAS) method, both β and γ emission decay energies were measured at selected cooling times as early as a few tens of seconds after the irradiation ended. After two campaigns, in 1996 and 2000 more than 74 different samples had been irradiated, the results published. Full report is available in [7]

4.1. Nickel simulations

Although the simulation protocols are identical for all libraries it is noticeable from Fig 5 and Table IV (right) that not all libraries perform adequately in predicting the decay heat arising from this common element. The unique reason for ENDF/B-VIII.1 to poorly performed relates to the lack of isomeric state residual production in the Ni58,-60,-62 (n,p) channels provided.

Figure 5. FNS Nickel decay heat results – C/E, predominant isotopes

4.2. Iridium simulations

The case for iridium in Fig. 6 and Table IV (left) is of the same nature as the one of Nickel, missing altogether for ENDF/B-VIII.1 or inadequately branched for JENDL-5 residual isomeric state production, JEFF-4.0 have them because of TENDL. However, the most interesting feature is that both experimental and simulated decay heat results tend to increase with cooling time. A counter intuitive feature for decay processes that is however explained by the presence of predominant radioactive decay daughters having a longer half-life than the one of its parent.

FNS-00 5 Min. Irradiation - Ir

Figure 6. FNS Irridium decay heat – C/E, predominant isotopes

5. CONCLUSIONS

The experimental time-dependent decay-power measurement program at JAEA Fusion Neutron Source and the compilation of fifteen independent fission event “burst” program carried out between 1964 and 2002 in France, Germany, Sweden, the UK, USA and Japan combined with the code simulations protocols performed in this study provide a unique check of the calculational methods and nuclear databases associated with the prediction of decay power for the set of material samples and irradiation conditions analysed. The results of such broad fission, fusion and encompassing Verification and Validation (V&V) exercises give confidence in the deployment, robustness and validity of such complex simulations tools and protocols.

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REFERENCES

- [1] J.-Ch. Sublet, J. Eastwood, J. Morgan, M. Gilbert, M. Fleming, and W. Arter, "FISPACT-II: An Advanced Simulation System for Activation, Transmutation and Material Modelling," **Nuclear Data Sheets**, vol. 139, pp. 77 – 137, 2017. Special Issue on Nuclear Reaction Data. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nds.2017.01.002>
- [2] A.J.M. Plompen, et al "The joint evaluated fission and fusion nuclear data library, JEFF-3.3" [The European Physical Journal A](#), & "JEFF-4.0" (Open Access)
- [3] O. Iwamoto, N. Iwamoto, S. Kunieda, F. Minato, S. Nakayama, Y. Abe, et al., "Japanese evaluated nuclear data library version 5: JENDL-5", *J. Nucl. Sci. Technol.*, **60**(1), 1-60 (2023). [DOI: 10.1080/00223131.2022.2141903](https://doi.org/10.1080/00223131.2022.2141903) (Open Access).
- [4] G.P.A Nobre et al., "ENDF/B-VIII.1 nuclear data for science and technology." [BNL NNDC](#), (2025)
- [5] "Compilation of Nuclear Data Experiments for Radiation Characterisation (CoNDERC)" (2019). URL <https://nds.iaea.org/conderc/>
- [6] R. Goodwin, J.-Ch. Sublet, J. Hollis "Prediction of Fission Events Using FISPACT-II – JEFF-4.0, JENDL-5.0 and ENDF/B-VIII.1: Cross-sections, Decay Data and Neutron-induced Fission Yields" Tech. Rep. UKAEA-R(26)xx, (2026).
- [7] J. Hollis, J.-Ch. Sublet, M. Gilbert, G. Bailey "Fusion decay heat validation, FISPACT-II & JEFF-4.0, JENDL-5 and ENDF/B-VIII.1, nuclear data libraries" Tech. Rep. UKAEA-R(26)xx, (2026)